

Identifying NFDI Consortia with Persistent Identifiers (v1.0)

Recommendations of
PID4NFDI Coordination Hub

D1.2 NFDI-wide PID Guidelines

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About

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Abstract

This document presents the official recommendation of the PID4NFDI Coordination Hub for assigning persistent identifiers (PIDs) to the consortia of Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI).

To ensure consistent, interoperable, and FAIR identification across the NFDI landscape, PID4NFDI recommends the use of DataCite Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) with the resource type "Project" as the authoritative identifiers for NFDI consortia.

The proposed approach reflects the specific nature of NFDI consortia as collaborative, project-based alliances without independent legal status, which fall outside the scope of organizational PID systems such as ROR (Research Organization Registry). At the same time, this approach avoids potential conflicts or problems with the German revenue administration.

DataCite DOIs offer a mature, transparent, and provenance-controlled infrastructure that aligns with NFDI's strategic goals for sustainable and machine-actionable metadata management.

Complementary PID systems - including ROR for participating institutions, Wikidata IRIs for semantic integration into the Linked Open Data ecosystem, and RAiD (Research Activity Identifier) for tracking project relationships once operational in Germany - are acknowledged as part of a layered and interoperable PID framework for the future.

By adopting this model for the time being, NFDI strengthens the discoverability, attribution, and long-term accessibility of its research consortia, ensuring their integration within the global PID ecosystem and alignment with international best practices in research infrastructure governance.

1. Introduction

This document provides the official recommendation of the PID4NFDI Coordination Hub for assigning persistent identifiers (PIDs) to NFDI consortia.

It aims to harmonize current practices and address existing gaps in organizational identification across the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI).

The recommended approach is to use DataCite DOIs with the resource type “Project” to identify NFDI consortia in a sustainable, interoperable, and FAIR manner.

2. About the PID4NFDI Coordination Hub

The PID4NFDI Coordination Hub, established under the Base4NFDI-funded project PID4NFDI, serves as the central point of coordination for persistent identifier (PID) activities within the National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI). Its core mandate is to promote consistent and interoperable PID practices across all NFDI consortia, ensuring that research outputs, actors, and infrastructures are globally discoverable and persistently linked.

The Hub’s mission is to align PID services, metadata standards, and implementation strategies across domains, creating a shared foundation for interoperability and long-term data integrity.

Working in close collaboration with NFDI stakeholders including the project partners DataCite, the Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG), the TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology, and the Helmholtz Open Science Office, the Coordination Hub develops practical guidance, shared tools, and support mechanisms **that ensure alignment between NFDI and the international PID landscape.**

3. Why NFDI Consortia Need Persistent Identifiers

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are a cornerstone of sustainable and FAIR research infrastructures. They ensure that entities, such as datasets, people, organizations, and projects, can be unambiguously referenced, discovered, and connected to their outputs. This would significantly reduce the effort required to collect NFDI-wide output and report on its activities.

Identifying NFDI Consortia with Persistent Identifiers

For NFDI consortia, which often operate under multiple names and acronyms, PIDs provide:

- Unique and persistent identification – eliminating confusion caused by inconsistent naming (e.g., Mathematische Forschungsdateninitiative, Mathematical Research Data Initiative, MaRDI, mardi4nfdi).
- Attribution of activities and outputs – linking publications, datasets, and services to their respective consortium.
- Machine-readability and interoperability – enabling integration with DataCite, ORCID, EOSC, OpenAIRE, and related infrastructures.
- Visibility and recognition – improving discoverability and international visibility of NFDI consortia and their outputs.
- Support of the FAIR principles – providing the necessary organizational context for making data and services Findable and Reusable.

These benefits align with the strategic goals of NFDI and meet the expectations of funders, infrastructures, and the broader research community.

4. The NFDI Context

NFDI is a federated, multi-layered research data infrastructure composed of domain-specific and cross-cutting consortia. Each consortium is a collaborative, project-based alliance of multiple institutions, typically operating under a limited timeframe and without legal personality. This makes them distinct from conventional organizations and thus unsuitable for certain types of organizational PIDs (e.g., ROR).

The distributed and dynamic nature of NFDI requires a flexible yet authoritative approach to persistent identification, one that enables clear attribution and long-term resolution without imposing organizational constraints.

5. Recommendation: Assigning DataCite DOIs to NFDI Consortia

Core Recommendation

The PID4NFDI Coordination Hub recommends assigning **DataCite DOIs with resourceTypeGeneral = “Project”** to identify NFDI consortia. This approach provides a technically mature, interoperable, and provenance-controlled solution that aligns with both DataCite’s metadata schema and NFDI’s strategic goals for persistent, FAIR, and machine-actionable infrastructure.

Why DOIs?

DataCite DOIs, using the resource type “**Project**”, offer a robust and immediately deployable option that satisfies current operational needs while remaining compatible with future PID developments.

Key advantages include:

- Established infrastructure – DOIs are a proven, globally used standard supported by DataCite’s mature infrastructure and embedded across scholarly communication systems such as ORCID, OpenAIRE, and EOSC.
- Clear cost and service model – Membership pathways are transparent and affordable. For example, DataCite consortium membership via TIB costs approximately 350 EUR/year and allows for the registration for up to 2,000 DOIs.
- Flexibility – DOIs can be assigned not only to entire consortia but also to sub-projects, services, or infrastructure components. Linked PIDs allow hierarchical and relational structures between these entities to be represented explicitly.
- Compatibility – DOIs can later be linked to RAiDs, RORs, or Wikidata IRIs. Multiple identifiers for a single entity can coexist and complement each other, creating a rich, connected PID graph.
- Authoritative landing pages – The NFDI Association already maintains individual pages for each consortium at <https://www.nfdi.de/konsortien/>. These can serve as persistent DOI landing pages, ensuring long-term accessibility and resolution. The DOI redirect function also allows future flexibility, for example, redirecting to a consortium website or an NFDI-wide service catalogue entry.

Provenance and Authority

DataCite DOIs provide **traceable provenance** for every identifier. Each record contains metadata on its publisher, creation date, and update history, ensuring accountability and transparency.

Registration privileges are restricted to DataCite members or their delegated organizations.

That governance model ensures that the metadata indicating who created the record is accurate and accountable and is different from systems like ROR or Wikidata, where the pathways for creating or modifying records are community-driven but with varying levels of oversight. Wikidata is openly editable by anyone, with decisions emerging from community consensus. ROR, by contrast, operates through a structured review and approval process managed via GitHub issues and overseen by its steering groups. Even so, transparency has limits: for example, in withdrawal cases, the contact details or identity of the requester are not disclosed unless the requester shares them themselves.¹

¹ See: <https://github.com/ror-community/ror-updates/issues/14719#issuecomment-3348859860>.

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In short, both systems enable broad participation, but neither provides the strict, verifiable provenance tied to an authorized organization that DOI registration metadata guarantees.

Resource Type: Project vs. Award/Grant

To accurately describe NFDI consortia and their activities, it is crucial to distinguish between two different types of entities: projects and funding awards.

- **Project PIDs** describe the research activity itself, the people involved, the work performed, the outputs produced, and the lifecycle of the project.
- **Award/Grant PIDs** describe the funding decision, the organization providing the money, the program under which it was awarded, and the associated award or grant number.

These are separate entities with distinct responsibilities and lifecycles. NFDI consortia are best aligned with the “project” category, as they represent coordinated research activities rather than funding bodies. Therefore, the appropriate DataCite designation is resourceTypeGeneral = “Project”.

Funding information, including funder name, funder ROR ID, and grant or award number, should be issued and managed by the funders themselves (e.g., the German Research Foundation, the European Commission). Funders are the authoritative source for award metadata, and they provide this information at the point of origin. Within a project PID, this funding information should appear only as related metadata that links the project to its financial support.

DataCite supports registration of both resource type Projects and Awards. Hence, we recommend that funders to use Award DOIs and NFDI consortia to **use Project DOIs**. NFDI consortia are not funders; they are the funded projects and are therefore best positioned to document project-level details.

Implementation Options

Several viable routes exist for registering DOIs for NFDI consortia and for NFDI e.V.:

1. **Direct DataCite membership** – Provides complete autonomy but incurs the highest cost.
2. **NFDI e.V. consortium membership** – Cost-effective and ensures metadata sovereignty at the association level. Furthermore, a centralized metadata collection effort encourages metadata harmonization and completeness based on standardized reporting requirements from NFDI e.V.
3. **Registration via a third-party service provider (e.g., TIB)** – Suitable when only a few project DOIs are required. This model demands clear metadata maintenance workflows between the registering authority and project leads.
4. **Registration through spokesperson organizations** – *Recommended*. Over 90% of NFDI member institutions are already DataCite members (direct or consortium).

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This pathway gives project leaders full control of their consortium metadata, facilitates linking outputs and related research activities, and integrates naturally with institutional data workflows.

If option 4 is unavailable, option 2, consortium membership of NFDI e.V., is the next best alternative, ensuring governance continuity and metadata quality across consortia. Harvesting project DOIs into the NFDI-wide metadata catalogue would then require only a lightweight metadata template, with PID4NFDI providing support for its development.

6. Comparative Considerations

A balanced approach to PID selection requires understanding the strengths and limitations of each available system.

Below is a comparative overview of **ROR**, **Wikidata**, and **RAiD** in the context of identifying NFDI consortia.

ROR (Research Organization Registry)

Best suited for:

Organizations that are recognized, independent entities contributing to research outputs, as defined by [ROR's own inclusion criteria](#).

Current NFDI Status

The NFDI Association currently holds a **persistent identifier in ROR**: <https://ror.org/05qj6w324>. This record categorizes NFDI as an organization but does not indicate its role as a *funder*.

The *funder* designation is a recently added category following ROR's expansion to include funding organizations, a remit previously covered by Crossref's Funder ID system.

At the time of writing, only two NFDI consortia appear as active ROR entries:

- NFDI4DS: <https://ror.org/00bb4nn95>
Created: 2024-03-13 | Last modified: 2024-12-11
- MaRDI: <https://ror.org/04ncnzm65>
Created: 2024-02-13 | Last modified: 2024-12-11

Several other consortia, including DAPHNE4NFDI (<https://ror.org/03xrvbe74>) and PUNCH4NFDI (<https://ror.org/03f6sdf65>), were registered in 2024 but subsequently withdrawn. Most of these records share the same creation date (2024-09-14) and last modified date (2024-12-11), as a coordinated withdrawal. Because the NFDI consortia do not constitute independent entities but operate as project structures, the use of ROR IDs already raised concerns regarding the potential creation of unintended legal or tax-related

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implications which have been raised in internal discussions between representatives of several consortia.²

During this period, the MaRDI and NFDI4DS entries remained active.

ROR's governance model does not disclose who created or withdrew records, so the provenance of these submissions cannot be verified, illustrating one of the limitations of using ROR for a controlled consortium-level identification.

Why NFDI Consortia Fall Outside ROR's Scope

According to ROR's [official scope criteria](#), to be included in the registry an organization must:

- Demonstrate **independence from other organizations** to which it is related, and
- Not exist as a **subdivision within a single standalone organization or named entity**.

ROR explicitly lists the following entities as **out of scope**:

- University departments and faculties
- Funding programs and schemes
- **Projects or initiatives that are not organizations**
- Single-person consultancies
- Journals

NFDI consortia, by their structure and mandate, do not meet these criteria.

They are **projects and alliances** formed through time-bound funding calls, typically coordinated by multiple institutions, and they do not operate as independent or standalone organizations. They have no separate governance, staff, or institutional affiliation that is distinct from their member organizations.

In contrast, the **NFDI Association (NFDI e.V.)** is a legally registered body with independent governance and representation, fully within ROR's organizational scope. This explains why the NFDI Association justifiably retains a valid ROR ID, while individual consortia do not. Assigning RORs to consortia would misrepresent their organizational status and contradict ROR's stated inclusion policy.

Pros:

- Widely recognized and interoperable with other PID systems (e.g., Crossref, ORCID).
- Provides stable, resolvable identifiers for independent research organizations.
- Open, community-driven process for proposing and updating records.

² See Evaluation Criteria from ROR:

<https://github.com/ror-community/ror-updates/wiki/Curator-Evaluation-Workflow:-New-Records#hecklist-for-evaluating-new-organizations>.

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Cons:

- Community registration via GitHub allows anyone to submit entries, reducing provenance control.
- The governance model does not track or disclose who created or removed records.
- Scope explicitly excludes projects and non-organizational initiatives such as NFDI consortia.
- Role differentiation (e.g., funder, participant, project) is still limited in metadata granularity.

Summary:

ROR plays an essential role in identifying organizations within the research ecosystem, such as host institutions or the NFDI Association itself.

However, NFDI consortia currently fall outside the registry's defined scope, as they are collaborative, project-based initiatives rather than distinct, independent organizations.

The recent creation and withdrawal of multiple consortium records underscore the unsuitability of ROR for this purpose and validate the recommendation to use DataCite DOIs (resourceTypeGeneral = Project) as the more suitable solution for identifying NFDI consortia.

Wikidata

Best suited for:

Linking and representing entities in the semantic web and the broader Linked Open Data (LOD) ecosystem.

Overview

Wikidata provides a freely available, community-curated platform for identifying and describing research-related entities.

All 26 NFDI consortia (plus Base4NFDI) already have entries in Wikidata, many of which include details such as participant institutions, co-applicants, and related initiatives.

These records are both **machine-readable** (in RDF and multiple serializations) and **human-readable**, making them immediately usable for discovery and semantic integration.

Strengths

- Existing coverage – All NFDI consortia are already represented.
- Rich metadata – Entries often include co-applicants, participant organizations, and project links.
- Interoperability – Data is published as RDF in multiple serializations, accessible via an API and SPARQL query service.

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- Collaborative curation – Anyone can contribute updates through the Wikidata editor, with full version history.
- Linked Open Data integration – Entries are automatically part of the global knowledge graph.
- Open and cost-free – No membership or fees required.
- Cross-linking potential – Wikidata IRIs can easily reference DOIs, RORs, or RAIDs, extending NFDI's PID network into the semantic web.

Limitations

- Limited harmonization framework – Records are curated collaboratively, with no formal validation or approval mechanism. Data quality control and consistency rely heavily on the engagement and expertise of the community rather than uniform standards across domains.
- Mutable content – Metadata can be modified by anyone at any time. This flexibility supports rapid updates but also demands caution when verification is required for authoritative use. This mutability complicates citation, reproducibility, and long-term reference and requires capturing a fixed state of information.
- Limited provenance control – While persistent, Wikidata IRIs lack DOI-level provenance and the controlled assignment process that ensures metadata authenticity and traceability.

Example entries

- BERD@NFDI: <https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q108542181>
- Base4NFDI: <https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q113544452>
- MaRDI: <https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q108327788>
- FAIRmat: <https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q108542373>
- NFDI4DataScience: <https://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q108542422>
(A complete list of consortia IRIs is available via [SPARQL query](#).)

Summary

Wikidata IRIs serve as **valuable complementary identifiers** for discovery, semantic enrichment, and integration into the global Linked Open Data graph.

They are well suited for contextual linking and interoperability but lack the provenance and governance standards required for authoritative PID assignment.

Accordingly, Wikidata IRIs should complement, not replace, DOIs, serving as secondary identifiers referenced in DOI metadata to enhance NFDI's visibility and connectivity across the semantic web. These links can be established directly through the relatedIdentifier field in DataCite metadata, as outlined in Section 5.

RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)

Best suited for:

Tracking research activities, projects, and their relationships over time.

Pros:

- Potentially aligns conceptually well with the notion of consortia as research projects.
- Designed to capture relationships between activities, people, institutions, and outputs.
- Offers its own registry, including landing pages.
- Potentially highly interoperable once fully operational.

Cons:

- Still under development; not yet established or available for use in Germany.
- Governance and cost models remain in flux and limited to a few national contexts (e.g., Australia, Netherlands). A model for integration in EOSC is not available yet.
- Integration pathways with NFDI infrastructures are not yet mature.

Summary:

At the time of writing, RAiD is not yet operational in Germany. Once it becomes available, this recommendation will be reviewed and updated to ensure continued alignment with international best practices and to support DOI-RAiD cross-linking for tracking project relationships.

7. Summary & Conclusion

This recommendation does not replace or compete with other PID systems.

Instead, it positions DataCite DOIs (resourceTypeGeneral = “Project”) as the authoritative identifier for NFDI consortia, integrating seamlessly with complementary PID systems to form a connected, interoperable ecosystem.

ROR (Research Organization Registry)

ROR remains the appropriate identifier for organizations such as universities, research institutes, and the NFDI Association (NFDI e.V.), all of which fall within ROR’s inclusion criteria.

RORs can be linked to DOI metadata through the *relatedIdentifier* property to represent institutional structures, such as host organizations, member institutions, or funders.

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However, as ROR explicitly excludes projects and initiatives that are not organizations, it is **not suitable** for identifying NFDI consortia themselves in their current form.³

RAiD (Research Activity Identifier)

Once RAiD becomes fully operational in Germany, this recommendation will be revisited to ensure alignment with international best practices and to enable DOI-RAiD linking for tracking project relationships.

Wikidata IRIs

Wikidata IRIs already exist for all NFDI consortia and can serve as **semantic anchors** within the Linked Open Data (LOD) landscape. They provide rich, RDF-based metadata that is openly queryable, versioned, and machine-readable.

Although community-curated rather than authority-verified, Wikidata records offer valuable contextual links to related entities (e.g., institutions, projects, and topics). These IRIs can be referenced in DOI metadata to enhance discoverability and semantic integration across infrastructures.

In summary:

- **DOIs** serve as the authoritative, provenance-rich identifiers for NFDI consortia, ideally managed by the consortia.
- **RORs** identify the organizations participating in or governing those consortia.
- **RAiDs** (when available) will complement DOI records to capture project-level relationships.
- **Wikidata IRIs** provide semantic enrichment and integration into the global Linked Open Data graph.

Together, these systems form a **layered, interoperable PID framework** that combines authoritative identification with rich semantic connectivity, advancing the FAIR and interoperable infrastructure goals of NFDI.

³ On reforming the current structure of NFDI consortia, see Wissenschaftsrat (2025): Strukturevaluation der Nationalen Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI), pp.66-69. <https://doi.org/10.57674/wcdc-6d36>.